

Re-Imagining Wildlife Conflict Resolution in Tanzania: Integrating Alternative Dispute Resolution Mechanisms into the Legal Framework for Conservation

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Abstract:

Human-wildlife conflicts (HWC) present a persistent challenge to wildlife conservation and community livelihoods in Tanzania, particularly in areas adjacent to national parks and protected zones. The prevailing legal framework, most notably the Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022], lacks explicit recognition or integration of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms such as mediation and negotiation. Instead, conflict responses remain heavily bureaucratic, punitive, or compensatory, excluding affected communities from participatory redress. This article explores the normative, institutional, and practical implications of this legal omission by employing doctrinal, empirical, and comparative legal methodologies. The article analyses domestic legal instruments, stakeholder perceptions from Ruaha Village, and best practices from Kenya and South Africa to assess the feasibility of integrating ADR into Tanzania's wildlife conservation regime. It argues that structured ADR mechanisms can enhance access to justice, reduce litigation burdens, foster community trust, and promote sustainable coexistence between humans and wildlife. The article concludes with practical reform recommendations aimed at embedding ADR within Tanzania's conservation laws and policies, thus offering a for inclusive environmental governance.

Keywords: Alternative Dispute Resolution, Human-Wildlife Conflicts, Conservation Laws, Community Participation, Tanzania, South Africa, Kenya.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Human-wildlife conflicts (HWC) are a recurring challenge in Tanzania's conservation landscape, particularly in communities adjacent to protected areas like Ruaha and Serengeti. These conflicts often involve crop destruction, livestock loss, or threats to human safety due to wildlife encroachment, largely driven by habitat fragmentation and land-use pressure.¹ Despite the magnitude of the problem, Tanzania's legal framework especially the Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022] lacks mechanisms for participatory conflict resolution, relying instead on state-led compensation or reactive interventions.²

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), which includes mediation and negotiation, offers accessible and culturally grounded methods to resolve such disputes.³ ADR has been integrated into conservation frameworks in Kenya and South Africa, where it improves access to justice and fosters community involvement.⁴ In Tanzania, however, ADR remains absent from statutory wildlife governance, despite its alignment with traditional dispute practices in rural settings.

This article explores the legal and institutional implications of this gap by combining doctrinal analysis of Tanzanian statutes, field research from Ruaha Village, and comparative lessons from neighbouring jurisdictions. The findings suggest that affected communities are not only willing to use ADR but are currently excluded by law and policy.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology; Section 3 explores HWC in Tanzania; Section 4 reviews domestic legal frameworks; Section 5 offers comparative analysis; Section 6 builds the case for ADR; Section 7 identifies barriers; Section 8 proposes reforms; and Section 9 concludes with policy implications.

2. LEGAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article adopts a triangulated legal research methodology combining doctrinal, empirical, and comparative approaches to critically evaluate the normative and institutional omission of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms in Tanzania's legal framework for managing human-wildlife conflicts (HWC). Each methodological component is employed to ensure that the analysis is not only grounded in statutory and policy interpretation but also informed by lived realities and regional best practices.

¹Treves, A. et al. (2006). Co-managing human-wildlife conflicts: A review. *WCS Working Paper No. 12*, pp. 1-10.

²Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022], ss. 69-71.

³Brown, H. & Marriott, A. (2018). *ADR: Principles and Practice*. 4th ed., Sweet & Maxwell, pp. 5-7.

⁴National Environmental Management Act (South Africa), No. 107 of 1998, s. 17; Wildlife Conservation and Management Act (Kenya), No. 47 of 2013, s. 102.

2.1 Doctrinal Legal Research

Doctrinal legal research also known as “black letter law” methodology is the foundational approach of this study. It involves the critical analysis of primary and secondary legal sources to identify gaps, ambiguities, and opportunities for legal reform.⁵ This approach allows for an authoritative examination of how Tanzanian statutes, subsidiary legislation, and policy frameworks currently address wildlife conflict resolution and whether they incorporate ADR tools such as mediation, negotiation, and conciliation.

Key statutes reviewed include the Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022], which governs wildlife protection and conflict responses; the Environmental Management Act [Cap. 191 R.E. 2022], which provides general provisions on environmental regulation and appeals mechanisms; the Village Land Act [Cap. 114 R.E. 2019], which acknowledges community-based dispute resolution through Village Land Councils; and the Local Government (District Authorities) Act [Cap. 287 R.E. 2002], which establishes participatory governance at the grassroots level. The Arbitration Act [Cap. 15 R.E. 2020] was also examined for general principles governing ADR processes in civil disputes.

Doctrinal analysis was supplemented by jurisprudence from Tanzanian courts—though limited in environmental ADR—as well as international environmental law instruments such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)⁶ and the Revised African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (Maputo Convention).⁷ Legal interpretive techniques—including the literal, golden, and purposive rules—were applied to interpret statutory texts in light of constitutional values, practical realities, and legislative intent. Research sources included verified legal databases such as TanzLII, HeinOnline, JSTOR, and LexisNexis.

2.2 Empirical Legal Research

To complement the doctrinal inquiry, the study employed empirical legal research methods aimed at capturing the practical experiences and perceptions of communities affected by human-wildlife conflicts. Empirical methods are increasingly recognised in

⁵ Hutchinson, T. & Duncan, N. (2012). Defining and Describing What We Do: Doctrinal Legal Research. *Deakin Law Review*, 17(1), 83–119.

⁶ Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), adopted 5 June 1992, entered into force 29 December 1993, Article 8(j).

⁷ African Union, Revised African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (Maputo Convention), adopted 11 July 2003, Article XV.

environmental law scholarship for providing insights into how legal norms function (or fail to function) in real-world contexts.⁸

The primary site for fieldwork was Ruaha Village, located in Iringa Region adjacent to Ruaha National Park, one of the largest protected ecosystems in East Africa and a known hotspot for wildlife-induced damage. Semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with a purposive sample of stakeholders, including subsistence farmers, village leaders, park officers from the Tanzania Wildlife Authority (TAWA), ward tribunal officials, and civil society actors involved in conservation. This method ensured the inclusion of diverse voices based on age, gender, occupation, and institutional affiliation.

All participants gave informed consent, and the study obtained ethical clearance from local authorities in accordance with the University of Dar es Salaam research ethics guidelines. Data were anonymised and thematically coded to identify common grievances, preferred resolution methods, and perceptions of ADR. The empirical component enhanced the study's legitimacy by ensuring that reform recommendations are responsive to the lived experiences of affected communities.

2.3 Comparative Legal Analysis

The comparative dimension of this study assesses how other African jurisdictions—particularly Kenya and South Africa—have successfully integrated ADR into wildlife conservation and environmental governance. Comparative law, when properly contextualised, can serve as a powerful tool for legal innovation and policy transfer.⁹

In Kenya, the Wildlife Conservation and Management Act, 2013, recognises ADR as a formal component of dispute settlement under section 102. Kenya also hosts a robust Alternative Dispute Resolution Framework within the Kenya Revenue Authority and other state institutions, demonstrating institutional support for non-adversarial resolution mechanisms.¹⁰

In South Africa, the National Environmental Management Act (NEMA), No. 107 of 1998, expressly provides for environmental mediation and conciliation in section 17. Additionally, the Department of Environmental Affairs has issued Guidelines on Mediation and Conciliation in Environmental Disputes (2016), promoting ADR as a tool

⁸ Cownie, F. & Bradney, A. (2013). *Socio-Legal Studies: A Challenge to the Doctrinal Approach*. In: Cane, P. & Kritzer, H.M. (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of Empirical Legal Research*. Oxford University Press, pp. 33–50.

⁹ Zweigert, K. & Kötz, H. (1998). *An Introduction to Comparative Law*. 3rd ed. Oxford: Clarendon Press, p. 15.

¹⁰ Kenya Revenue Authority. (2021). *ADR Framework Manual*. Retrieved from: <https://www.kra.go.ke> on 26 July 2025.

for strengthening environmental democracy and access to justice.¹¹ These jurisdictions were selected based on their ecological and legal similarities to Tanzania, including pluralistic legal systems, community-based conservation frameworks, and decentralised administrative structures.

By analysing institutional arrangements, legal mandates, and stakeholder responses in Kenya and South Africa, the study derives transferrable insights into how Tanzania might reform its statutory framework to accommodate ADR within conservation law.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Understanding the Nature of Human-Wildlife Conflicts in Tanzania

Human-wildlife conflict (HWC) in Tanzania represents one of the most acute and persistent environmental governance challenges, particularly in areas bordering national parks and game reserves. These conflicts occur when wildlife adversely impacts human welfare by damaging crops, preying on livestock, threatening human safety, or destroying property while humans, in turn, retaliate by harming or displacing wildlife.¹² The scale and intensity of HWC have been increasing in recent decades, largely due to demographic growth, habitat fragmentation, and competing land-use pressures.

Tanzania, which hosts over 30% of its land under protected status¹³ and is home to ecologically rich areas such as the Serengeti, Ruaha, Mikumi, and Ngorongoro, often witnesses these conflicts along the edges of these conservation zones. In such buffer communities, elephants, lions, leopards, and buffalos are the most frequent sources of conflict. For instance, elephants have been documented as the primary cause of crop destruction in regions like Iringa, Morogoro, and Manyara.¹⁴ In Ruaha, where this study's empirical research is anchored, local residents frequently report nocturnal crop raids and livestock killings, particularly during the dry season when wildlife encroaches into human settlements in search of water and food.

The leading cause of HWC in Tanzania is habitat encroachment driven by agricultural expansion and human settlement. As the population exceeds 65 million and continues to grow, rural communities have progressively expanded farming into wildlife migratory

¹¹ Department of Environmental Affairs (South Africa). (2016). *Guidelines on Mediation and Conciliation in Environmental Disputes*. Pretoria: Government of South Africa. Retrieved from: https://www.dffe.gov.za/sites/default/files/docs/guidelines_mediation_environmental_disputes2016.pdf on 26 July 2025.

¹² Woodroffe, R., Thirgood, S., & Rabinowitz, A. (2005). *People and Wildlife: Conflict or Coexistence?* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 1–3.

¹³URT (United Republic of Tanzania), Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism. (2021). *Wildlife Sector Status Report*, p. 7.

¹⁴WWF Tanzania. (2020). *Human-Wildlife Conflict Mitigation Strategy 2020–2025*. Retrieved from: https://www.wwf.or.tz/media_centre/publications/ on 26 July 2025.

routes and dispersal areas.¹⁵ The fragmentation of these habitats due to roads, farms, and settlements restricts animal movement and forces wildlife into closer proximity with humans. While Tanzania's Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022] acknowledges the challenge of "problem animals" under sections 69–71, its emphasis remains on reactive measures such as lethal control and limited monetary consolation, rather than conflict prevention or dialogue-based interventions. The Act defines a "problem animal" under Section 3 as any wild animal that poses a threat to human life or causes damage to property. This includes species that repeatedly raid crops, attack livestock, or otherwise interfere with human activity.

Inadequate land-use planning compounds the problem. Most village land-use plans do not incorporate wildlife corridors or designated buffer zones. As a result, disputes arise over land tenure, grazing rights, and access to water sources conflicts that often escalate into legal confrontations or retaliatory actions by villagers against wildlife.¹⁶ Moreover, many conservation policies have historically been formulated in a top-down manner, excluding the voices of communities that bear the brunt of wildlife proximity.¹⁷ Consequently, perceptions that the state values animals over people are widespread among residents near protected areas.

Another contributing factor is the inadequacy of the current compensation regime. Although the Wildlife Conservation Act allows for the issuance of consolation payments in cases of death, injury, or property damage caused by wildlife, such payments are rarely timely or adequate.¹⁸ Many victims are unaware of the procedures involved, and even when claims are successfully lodged, disbursements are often delayed or underpaid. A study by the Tanzanian Natural Resource Forum found that over 60% of respondents in conflict-prone areas had never received compensation despite reporting damage.¹⁹ These failures deepen community resentment and fuel cycles of violence against animals.

Human-wildlife conflict also has deep psychosocial effects. Families living under constant threat of crop raids or livestock attacks experience stress, disrupted livelihoods, and a sense of abandonment by the state.²⁰ Over time, these grievances erode community trust in conservation authorities, particularly the Tanzania Wildlife Authority (TAWA) and

¹⁵Nelson, F., Lindsey, P., & Balme, G. (2013). Trophy hunting and lion conservation: A question of governance. *Oryx*, 47(4), 501–509.

¹⁶Sachedina, H. (2008). *Wildlife is Our Oil: Conservation, Livelihoods and NGOs in the Tarangire Ecosystem, Tanzania*. Oxford University DPhil Thesis, p. 84.

¹⁷Benjaminsen, T. A., Goldman, M. J., Minwary, M. Y., & Maganga, F. P. (2013). Wildlife Management in Tanzania: State Control, Rent Seeking and Community Resistance. *Development and Change*, 44(5), 1087–1109.

¹⁸TAWIRI (Tanzania Wildlife Research Institute). (2019). *Policy Brief on Human-Wildlife Conflicts in Tanzania*, p. 3.

¹⁹ Tanzania Natural Resource Forum (TNRF). (2016). *Community Experiences of Wildlife Compensation and Conflict Resolution in Tanzania*. Retrieved from: https://www.tnrf.org/files/Wildlife_Compensation_Report_TNRF.pdf on 26 July 2025.

²⁰Dickman, A. J. (2010). Complexities of conflict: The importance of considering social factors for effectively resolving human–wildlife conflict. *Animal Conservation*, 13(5), 458–466.

park management bodies. In response, some communities resort to illegal deterrents such as snares, poisoning, or coordinated wildlife killings practices that undermine conservation efforts and can push endangered species toward extinction.²¹

Despite these tensions, Tanzania's legal framework does not provide accessible, community-led mechanisms for resolving these conflicts. There is no legally recognised avenue for mediation, negotiation, or community dialogue in wildlife-related disputes. By contrast, local communities often cite traditional forums such as elders' gatherings (baraza la wazee) or village assemblies as effective and legitimate avenues for addressing such problems in a culturally sensitive and de-escalatory manner.²² However, these mechanisms lack formal recognition and legal enforceability under current wildlife law, rendering them marginalised and often disregarded by officialdom.

As human populations grow and climate variability further stresses land and resource access, the frequency and severity of HWC are expected to rise.²³ This reality underscores the urgent need for proactive, inclusive, and context-sensitive conflict resolution mechanisms. Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) particularly mediation and negotiation offer a promising pathway to restore trust, prevent escalation, and build consensus between communities and conservation authorities. Yet, as the next section explores, the existing Tanzanian legal framework neither promotes nor supports such approaches in wildlife governance.

3.2 The Legal and Policy Framework Governing Wildlife Conflict Resolution in Tanzania

Tanzania's wildlife conservation governance is principally anchored in statutory and administrative instruments designed to protect biodiversity while managing competing land-use demands. However, a close review reveals that while these instruments address certain aspects of conflict resolution, they fail to integrate Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) as a formal mechanism for managing human-wildlife conflicts (HWC). The resulting legal vacuum has fostered state-centric, bureaucratic, and often adversarial approaches to conflict management—approaches that are ill-suited for resolving disputes that are relational, spatial, and recurring in nature.

3.2.1 The Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022]

The principal legislation governing wildlife management in Tanzania is the Wildlife Conservation Act (WCA). Enacted to consolidate laws relating to the protection,

²¹TRAFFIC. (2021). *Poisoning Africa's Wildlife: Human–Wildlife Conflict and the Illegal Use of Poison*, p. 9.

²²Massawe, D. & Ndalaha, M. (2020). Traditional Conflict Resolution and Environmental Governance: Lessons from Northern Tanzania. *East African Journal of Peace & Human Rights*, 26(1), 45–67.

²³FAO. (2023). *Managing Conflicts Between People and Wildlife: Climate Change Dimensions*, Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization, Retrieved from: <https://www.fao.org/publications> on 26 July 2025.

conservation, and sustainable use of wildlife resources, the Act also provides mechanisms for managing conflicts involving wildlife. Under Section 69, wildlife officers are authorised to destroy "problem animals" that pose a threat to human life or property.²⁴ In Section 71, the Act provides for "consolation payments" in instances where wildlife causes human death, injury, or material damage.²⁵

While these provisions acknowledge the existence of HWC, they are largely reactive, focusing on post-incident remedies rather than preventive or participatory resolution. Notably absent from the Act is any reference to mediation, conciliation, or negotiation as viable alternatives to state-imposed decisions. Even where community participation is mentioned such as under Section 31, which provides for the establishment of Wildlife Management Areas (WMAs) there is no corresponding provision that empowers such communities to engage in structured ADR for resolving wildlife-related disputes.²⁶ This omission represents a normative gap, particularly given the socio-environmental complexity of HWC.

3.2.2 The Environmental Management Act [Cap. 191 R.E. 2022]

The Environmental Management Act (EMA) provides a framework for environmental governance in Tanzania and establishes the National Environmental Management Council (NEMC) as a central coordinating body. Although the Act includes provisions for dispute resolution, they are narrowly tailored to administrative and regulatory appeals. For instance, Section 204 establishes the Environmental Appeals Tribunal, which hears appeals against decisions made by environmental authorities.²⁷ However, the Tribunal follows quasi-judicial procedures and does not accommodate non-adversarial dispute resolution mechanisms such as mediation or negotiation, particularly in cases involving communities and conservation agencies.

Further, the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) procedures under the Act require stakeholder consultations during project planning, but do not extend to post-conflict community engagement once environmental harm or HWC occurs. Thus, while the EMA provides a basis for procedural participation, it fails to promote ADR as a tool for resolving environmental disputes arising from wildlife interactions.

3.2.3 The Village Land Act [Cap. 114 R.E. 2019]

The Village Land Act contains the most explicit statutory support for ADR within Tanzania's legal system. Under Section 60, the Act mandates the establishment of Village

²⁴ Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022], s. 69.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, s. 71.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, s. 31.

²⁷ Environmental Management Act [Cap. 191 R.E. 2022], s. 204.

Land Councils, which are authorised to mediate disputes over land ownership and use.²⁸ These councils embody many ADR principles, including informality, flexibility, consensus-building, and local legitimacy.²⁹ However, their jurisdiction is expressly limited to land disputes and does not extend to HWC unless the conflict is tangentially connected to land tenure or use rights.

Moreover, there is no mechanism for coordination between Village Land Councils and wildlife management authorities, such as TAWA or the Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism, which limits the potential for cross-sectoral conflict resolution. This sectoral isolation curtails the relevance and utility of the Act in addressing the multisectoral nature of HWC.

3.2.4 The Local Government (District Authorities) Act [Cap. 287 R.E. 2002]

This Act establishes Village Councils, Ward Development Committees, and District Councils, which have statutory mandates to promote local development, environmental management, and peacekeeping. Under Section 111, Ward Tribunals are authorised to mediate minor civil disputes and promote community harmony.³⁰ However, similar to the Village Land Act, these forums are not specifically empowered to handle HWC, and no operational framework exists to involve wildlife stakeholders such as park rangers or conservation NGOs—in these dispute resolution processes.

Even where community mediation occurs informally, such settlements lack legal enforceability, and are frequently disregarded by state officials and wildlife management authorities. The absence of a formal interface between community-based institutions and conservation entities renders the system structurally inadequate for managing the socio-ecological dimensions of wildlife-related disputes.

3.2.5 International Legal Commitments

At the international level, Tanzania is party to instruments that support non-judicial and community-based environmental dispute resolution. Article 8(j) of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) calls for the recognition of traditional knowledge and customary governance in conservation, including conflict resolution.³¹ Similarly, Article XV of the Revised African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (Maputo Convention) urges states to resolve natural resource conflicts through

²⁸ Village Land Act [Cap. 114 R.E. 2019], s. 60.

²⁹ Peter, C. M. (1997). *Human Rights in Tanzania: Selected Cases and Materials*. Dar es Salaam: Rudiger Köppe Verlag, p. 87.

³⁰ Local Government (District Authorities) Act [Cap. 287 R.E. 2002], s. 111.

³¹ Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Article 8(j).

negotiation, mediation, and other peaceful means.³² However, these provisions have not been domesticated into Tanzanian legislation, meaning that their aspirational value remains unfulfilled in practice.

3.2.6 Institutional Fragmentation and Absence of ADR Guidelines

Tanzania's institutional architecture for wildlife management is heavily fragmented. Conflict resolution roles are split between the Tanzania Wildlife Authority (TAWA), local governments, and various conservation bodies, with no designated ADR coordination unit or policy guidelines for handling HWC. This fragmentation results in jurisdictional confusion, duplicated mandates, and inconsistent practices, all of which erode accountability and deter communities from seeking redress.³³ In contrast, countries like South Africa and Kenya have established specific protocols and mediation units to manage environmental disputes examples that Tanzania has yet to emulate.

In sum, Tanzania's current legal framework fails to provide for ADR mechanisms in the context of wildlife conflict resolution. The reliance on top-down, state-led interventions including compensation and lethal control leaves no formal space for dialogue-based, community-driven approaches. As a result, disputes fester, tensions escalate, and conservation outcomes are compromised. The following section explores how comparative experiences from Kenya and South Africa can offer practical lessons for remedying this legal and institutional shortfall.

3.3 Comparative Perspectives on ADR in Wildlife and Environmental Conflicts

The integration of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) into environmental governance and wildlife conflict management is gaining prominence globally. In Africa, countries such as Kenya and South Africa have taken deliberate steps to formalise ADR in their environmental legal systems, with demonstrable success in enhancing access to justice, reducing litigation, and building community trust in conservation institutions. These experiences offer instructive models for Tanzania, where the lack of legal and institutional support for ADR continues to limit conflict resolution options in wildlife governance.

3.3.1 Kenya: Formalising ADR in Conservation Law

Kenya has made significant strides in embedding ADR in its conservation framework through the Wildlife Conservation and Management Act, No. 47 of 2013. Under Section

³² Revised African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (Maputo Convention), Article XV.

³³ Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism (MNRT). (2017). *Wildlife Sector Review and Governance Report*, p. 22.

102, the Act requires the Kenya Wildlife Service (KWS) to promote cooperation and conflict resolution with communities through negotiation, mediation, and arbitration, particularly in areas affected by human-wildlife conflict.³⁴ This provision recognises that adversarial legal approaches often alienate communities and strain relationships, whereas ADR enables trust-building and mutually agreeable outcomes.

In addition to legislation, Kenya's Environment and Land Court Act, No. 19 of 2011, encourages parties to settle environmental disputes through ADR before proceeding to trial.³⁵ This is reinforced by Article 159(2)(c) of the Kenyan Constitution (2010), which mandates the judiciary to promote ADR, including traditional dispute resolution mechanisms that do not contravene constitutional principles.³⁶ These measures provide a constitutional and statutory foundation for integrating ADR into environmental decision-making and adjudication processes.

Moreover, Kenya has developed institutional frameworks beyond the judiciary. The Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA), though operating in a different regulatory sector, has established a specialised ADR Unit to handle tax-related disputes.³⁷ This demonstrates the government's recognition of ADR as a legitimate dispute resolution strategy even within formal administrative frameworks. The success of KRA's ADR program evidenced by increased compliance and reduced litigation illustrates the broader viability of institutionalised mediation in bureaucratic settings, including conservation agencies like KWS.

At the community level, Community Wildlife Associations (CWAs) are empowered under Section 40 of the Wildlife Act to participate in wildlife conservation and conflict resolution.³⁸ These groups often utilise traditional negotiation and mediation forums to manage disputes involving wildlife damage, grazing rights, and compensation claims. Such institutional pluralism enhances the social legitimacy and sustainability of conservation efforts, providing Tanzania with a practical example of how ADR can be embedded within both statutory and customary frameworks.

3.3.2 South Africa: Statutory Endorsement and Operational Guidelines

South Africa offers another progressive model where ADR is formally entrenched in environmental law. The National Environmental Management Act (NEMA), No. 107 of 1998, under Section 17, authorises the Minister to appoint mediators or facilitators for

³⁴ Wildlife Conservation and Management Act (Kenya), No. 47 of 2013, s. 102.

³⁵ Environment and Land Court Act (Kenya), No. 19 of 2011, s. 20.

³⁶ Constitution of Kenya (2010), Art. 159(2)(c).

³⁷ Kenya Revenue Authority. (2021). *ADR Framework Manual*. Retrieved from: <https://www.kra.go.ke> on 26 July 2025.

³⁸ Wildlife Conservation and Management Act (Kenya), s. 40.

resolving disputes related to the environment, biodiversity, or access to natural resources.³⁹ The provision explicitly mandates parties to consider mediation or conciliation before litigation, reflecting a restorative justice approach to environmental governance.

To operationalise this mandate, the Department of Environmental Affairs published the *Guidelines on Mediation and Conciliation in Environmental Disputes* (2016). These guidelines provide procedures for initiating ADR, selecting impartial facilitators, documenting outcomes, and ensuring follow-up.⁴⁰ The guidelines also emphasise inclusive stakeholder engagement, capacity building, and transparency principles that are critical for trust-building and legitimacy in conservation disputes.

In South Africa, ADR is also supported by judicial policy. Environmental courts encourage mediation, and the judiciary often refers complex disputes to independent mediators with subject-matter expertise.⁴¹ Furthermore, environmental NGOs and community organisations are recognised as legitimate participants in environmental ADR processes, helping to ensure that marginalised voices are heard and respected.

Importantly, South Africa's approach integrates legal enforceability into ADR outcomes. Mediation agreements may be registered with environmental tribunals or courts, thereby granting them the force of law.⁴² This provision enhances confidence in the ADR system, particularly among communities that might otherwise be wary of entering non-binding settlement processes.

3.3.3 Lessons for Tanzania

Both Kenya and South Africa demonstrate that ADR can be successfully integrated into conservation governance where there is (i) legal recognition of ADR mechanisms, (ii) institutional frameworks to support their operation, and (iii) procedural clarity and enforceability. These elements are notably absent in Tanzania's current wildlife conflict framework.

First, legal recognition through express statutory provisions ensures that ADR mechanisms are not seen as informal or subordinate to litigation. Kenya's Wildlife Act and South Africa's NEMA both clearly articulate the role and legitimacy of mediation and negotiation in conservation disputes.

³⁹ National Environmental Management Act (South Africa), No. 107 of 1998, s. 17.

⁴⁰ Department of Environmental Affairs (South Africa). (2016). *Guidelines on Mediation and Conciliation in Environmental Disputes*, pp. 1–20.

⁴¹ Du Plessis, A. (2009). Environmental Justice and ADR in South Africa: The Role of Environmental Courts. *South African Journal of Environmental Law and Policy*, 16(1), 1–24.

⁴² Glazewski, J. (2018). *Environmental Law in South Africa*. 3rd ed. Cape Town: LexisNexis, p. 623.

Second, institutional support is critical. Kenya's use of Community Wildlife Associations and South Africa's dedicated mediation units ensure that ADR is not only a theoretical right but also a functional system supported by trained professionals and community leaders.

Third, procedural safeguards such as transparent guidelines, registration of outcomes, and capacity development help maintain the integrity and credibility of ADR processes. These elements help bridge the gap between informal dialogue and formal justice, offering a template that Tanzania can adapt within its decentralised conservation and legal systems.

Given Tanzania's similar ecological conditions, legal pluralism, and community-based conservation efforts, the Kenyan and South African experiences offer transferrable models. While contextual adaptations are necessary, especially regarding customary land use practices and local governance structures, the comparative analysis strongly suggests that institutionalising ADR within Tanzanian wildlife law is both feasible and advantageous.

3.4 Evaluating the Case for ADR Integration in Tanzania's Wildlife Conflict Framework

Despite the existence of comprehensive legal frameworks regulating wildlife conservation in Tanzania, the statutory omission of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in managing human-wildlife conflicts (HWC) presents significant challenges to justice delivery, community participation, and effective environmental governance. This section synthesises doctrinal analysis, field observations, and regional experiences to argue for the urgent need to formally integrate ADR into Tanzania's wildlife conflict resolution framework.

3.4.1 Disconnect Between Legal Framework and Community Realities

Field data gathered from Ruaha Village, located adjacent to Ruaha National Park, highlights deep dissatisfaction among community members with current state-centric conflict response mechanisms. Interviews with farmers, village leaders, and local council officials revealed a consistent perception that consolation mechanisms under Section 71 of the Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022] are slow, opaque, and inadequately compensatory.⁴³ While the law provides for payments in cases of death, injury, or

⁴³ Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022], s. 71.

property damage caused by wildlife, in practice, delays in disbursement and difficulties in proving claims often render the compensation process ineffective.⁴⁴

Moreover, communities reported that wildlife-related complaints submitted to local authorities or TAWA often go unacknowledged, or are addressed in a top-down manner, without consultation or explanation. This absence of community engagement has bred resentment and mistrust, reinforcing perceptions that the law privileges wildlife over human welfare.⁴⁵ Notably, most respondents expressed strong support for mediation and community dialogue platforms, citing traditional practices such as “baraza la wazee” (council of elders) as effective mechanisms for resolving disputes related to land, grazing, and resource access. However, these traditional forums lack statutory recognition in the context of wildlife conflicts, making their decisions unenforceable and often ignored by public officials.⁴⁶

3.4.2 Benefits of ADR in Wildlife Conflict Contexts

The integration of ADR mechanisms into wildlife law offers several advantages. First, ADR promotes access to justice by reducing procedural complexity, cost, and time factors which deter rural and marginalised populations from pursuing formal litigation.⁴⁷ In conflict-prone areas like Ruaha, litigation is often impractical due to physical distance from courts, lack of legal representation, and the emotional toll of adversarial proceedings. Mediation, on the other hand, can be conducted locally, in Swahili, and in a culturally appropriate format, ensuring inclusivity and procedural fairness.⁴⁸

Second, ADR fosters restorative justice by addressing underlying interests rather than just legal rights. Unlike litigation, which often yields zero-sum outcomes, mediation enables disputants to co-create solutions such as community-managed fences, shared grazing plans, or compensation adjustments that acknowledge mutual concerns and promote coexistence.⁴⁹ This aligns with the ecosystem-based and participatory principles

⁴⁴ Tanzania Natural Resource Forum (TNRF). (2016). *Community Experiences of Wildlife Compensation and Conflict Resolution in Tanzania*, p. 5.

⁴⁵ Dickman, A. J. (2010). Complexities of conflict: The importance of considering social factors for effectively resolving human–wildlife conflict. *Animal Conservation*, 13(5), 458–466.

⁴⁶ Massawe, D. & Ndalaha, M. (2020). Traditional Conflict Resolution and Environmental Governance: Lessons from Northern Tanzania. *East African Journal of Peace & Human Rights*, 26(1), 45–67.

⁴⁷ Susskind, L. & Cruikshank, J. (2006). *Breaking the Impasse: Consensual Approaches to Resolving Public Disputes*. New York: Basic Books, pp. 75–88.

⁴⁸ UNEP. (2009). *Training Manual on Environmental Mediation*. Nairobi: United Nations Environment Programme. Retrieved from: <https://www.unep.org/resources/training-manual-environmental-mediation> on 26 July 2025.

⁴⁹ Fisher, R., Ury, W., & Patton, B. (2011). *Getting to Yes: Negotiating Agreement Without Giving In*. 3rd ed. Penguin Books, pp. 31–42.

underpinning both the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Maputo Convention, to which Tanzania is a party.⁵⁰

Third, ADR can improve the efficiency of public institutions by reducing the burden on TAWA, ward tribunals, and appellate bodies. By devolving first-line dispute resolution to village-level mediators or conservation committees, government agencies can redirect resources toward core enforcement and biodiversity management functions. The experience of Kenya's Community Wildlife Associations and South Africa's environmental mediation panels illustrates how such systems can be successfully institutionalised.⁵¹

Fourth, ADR mechanisms can help rebuild trust between local communities and conservation authorities—a critical prerequisite for effective wildlife protection. Empirical studies show that when communities are consulted and their grievances acknowledged, compliance with conservation rules increases, and retaliatory behaviours (such as poaching or habitat destruction) decline.⁵² Mediation and dialogue forums thus serve not only as dispute resolution tools, but also as platforms for long-term conflict transformation and civic reconciliation.

3.4.3 Community Readiness and Social Acceptance

The empirical data collected indicates that Tanzanian rural communities are culturally predisposed to ADR. Traditional conflict resolution methods based on dialogue, consensus, and communal healing have been used for generations in resolving family, land, and livestock disputes.⁵³ The absence of ADR in wildlife law is not due to social resistance, but rather a lack of legal recognition, training, and procedural support. This underscores the importance of a hybrid legal model that formalises and strengthens local dispute resolution capacities while providing legal enforceability and institutional support.

4. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This article has critically examined the normative and institutional absence of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms within Tanzania's legal framework for addressing human-wildlife conflicts (HWC). Drawing upon doctrinal legal analysis, empirical fieldwork from Ruaha Village, and comparative lessons from Kenya and South Africa, the

⁵⁰ Convention on Biological Diversity (1992), Article 8(j); Maputo Convention (2003), Article XV.

⁵¹ Department of Environmental Affairs (South Africa). (2016). *Guidelines on Mediation and Conciliation in Environmental Disputes*, p. 8; Kenya Wildlife Conservation and Management Act (2013), ss. 40 and 102.

⁵² Treves, A., Wallace, R. B., Naughton-Treves, L., & Morales, A. (2006). Co-managing human-wildlife conflicts: A review. *Wildlife Conservation Society Working Paper No. 12*, pp. 27–29.

⁵³ Peter, C. M. (1997). *Human Rights in Tanzania: Selected Cases and Materials*, pp. 86–88.

study reveals a substantial disconnect between the current state-centric, punitive approach to conflict resolution and the lived realities of rural communities affected by wildlife.

At the core of the problem is the Wildlife Conservation Act [Cap. 283 R.E. 2022], which, despite providing for consolation payments and control of problem animals, does not recognise or facilitate participatory, dialogue-based mechanisms such as mediation or negotiation. This omission is compounded by fragmented institutional mandates, weak community legal literacy, a lack of trained ADR personnel, and the absence of enforceable pathways for non-judicial settlements. Together, these factors have created an adversarial legal culture that frustrates local engagement, undermines conservation efforts, and breeds mistrust between communities and state authorities.

Conversely, evidence from Kenya's Wildlife Conservation and Management Act and South Africa's National Environmental Management Act (NEMA) demonstrates the transformative potential of ADR when embedded within statutory mandates and institutional frameworks. In both jurisdictions, structured ADR processes have led to improved conservation compliance, faster dispute resolution, and stronger community-government relationships.⁵⁴ These jurisdictions provide useful models for Tanzania, which shares similar legal traditions, ecological conditions, and challenges of balancing conservation with human development.

Empirical findings from Ruaha Village further underscore the community readiness and cultural familiarity with ADR. Residents consistently reported positive experiences with traditional dispute resolution mechanisms, and expressed willingness to engage in mediation or dialogue forums provided such processes are recognised by law, facilitated transparently, and supported by trusted mediators. These insights suggest that the barriers to ADR implementation in Tanzania are not sociocultural but rather legal, procedural, and institutional.

To address these systemic constraints, this article has proposed a comprehensive reform agenda, including Amending the Wildlife Conservation Act to expressly provide for ADR mechanisms, Establishing ADR Units within conservation authorities, Expanding the mandate of local governance institutions to mediate wildlife-related disputes, Developing a national ADR policy and training programs, Promoting public awareness and legal empowerment and Guaranteeing the enforceability of ADR outcomes through statutory registration.

These reforms are not only administratively feasible but also legally necessary to align Tanzania's wildlife governance with its constitutional commitment to justice, its regional obligations under the Maputo Convention, and its international commitments under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).⁵⁵ Furthermore, embedding ADR into wildlife

⁵⁴Department of Environmental Affairs (South Africa). (2016). *Guidelines on Mediation and Conciliation in Environmental Disputes*, pp. 3–6; Kenya Wildlife Conservation and Management Act (2013), s. 102.

⁵⁵Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), 1992, Art. 8(j); African Union Revised Maputo Convention, 2003, Art. XV.

law would operationalise the principles of procedural justice, decentralisation, and community participation—values already recognised in Tanzanian environmental and land law but inconsistently applied in the wildlife sector.

The policy implications are threefold. First, ADR offers a cost-effective, accessible, and restorative alternative to adversarial litigation in environmental disputes, particularly in rural and under-resourced regions. Second, by legitimising local knowledge systems and traditional resolution forums, ADR promotes legal pluralism and strengthens the social contract between the state and its citizens. Third, ADR enhances conservation outcomes by addressing root causes of conflict, fostering mutual accountability, and reducing retaliatory behaviours that threaten biodiversity.

As Tanzania continues to face growing pressures from population expansion, land-use change, and climate variability, the legal and institutional recalibration of its dispute resolution systems becomes ever more urgent. Institutionalising ADR within the wildlife conservation framework is not only a pragmatic reform it is a justice imperative, essential for safeguarding both community livelihoods and ecological sustainability in the decades to come.

References

- Benjaminsen, T. A., Goldman, M. J., Minwary, M. Y., & Maganga, F. P. (2013). Wildlife management in Tanzania: State control, rent seeking and community resistance. *Development and Change*, 44(5), 1087–1109.
- Brown, H., & Marriott, A. (2018). *ADR: Principles and Practice* (4th ed.). London: Sweet & Maxwell.
- Cownie, F., & Bradney, A. (2013). Socio-legal studies: A challenge to the doctrinal approach. In Cane, P., & Kritzer, H. M. (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Empirical Legal Research* (pp. 33–50). Oxford University Press.
- Dickman, A. J. (2010). Complexities of conflict: The importance of considering social factors for effectively resolving human–wildlife conflict. *Animal Conservation*, 13(5), 458–466.
- Du Plessis, A. (2009). Environmental justice and ADR in South Africa: The role of environmental courts. *South African Journal of Environmental Law and Policy*, 16(1), 1–24.
- Fisher, R., Ury, W., & Patton, B. (2011). *Getting to Yes: Negotiating Agreement Without Giving In* (3rd ed.). London: Penguin Books.
- Glazewski, J. (2018). *Environmental Law in South Africa* (3rd ed.). Cape Town: LexisNexis.
- Hutchinson, T., & Duncan, N. (2012). Defining and describing what we do: Doctrinal legal research. *Deakin Law Review*, 17(1), 83–119.
- Massawe, D., & Ndalaha, M. (2020). Traditional conflict resolution and environmental governance: Lessons from Northern Tanzania. *East African Journal of Peace & Human Rights*, 26(1), 45–67.
- Nelson, F., Lindsey, P., & Balme, G. (2013). Trophy hunting and lion conservation: A question of governance. *Oryx*, 47(4), 501–509.
- Peter, C. M. (1997). *Human Rights in Tanzania: Selected Cases and Materials*. Cologne: Rüdiger Köppe Verlag.
- Peter, C. M. (2008). *Widening the Door of Justice: Access to Justice and Legal Empowerment in Tanzania*. Dar es Salaam: Mkuki na Nyota.
- Riddell, J. (2014). Tanzania's local government reform program: Decentralisation and institutional capacity. *Journal of Public Administration and Development*, 34(1), 45–56.

Sachedina, H. (2008). *Wildlife is Our Oil: Conservation, Livelihoods and NGOs in the Tarangire Ecosystem, Tanzania* (Doctoral thesis). University of Oxford.

Susskind, L., & Cruikshank, J. (2006). *Breaking the Impasse: Consensual Approaches to Resolving Public Disputes*. New York: Basic Books.

Treves, A., Wallace, R. B., Naughton-Treves, L., & Morales, A. (2006). Co-managing human–wildlife conflicts: A review. *Wildlife Conservation Society Working Paper No. 12*, 1–72.

Woodroffe, R., Thirgood, S., & Rabinowitz, A. (2005). *People and Wildlife: Conflict or Coexistence?* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Zweigert, K., & Kötz, H. (1998). *An Introduction to Comparative Law* (3rd ed.). Oxford: Clarendon Press.

Statutes and Legal Instruments (Tanzania)

Arbitration Act, Cap. 15 R.E. 2020.

Environmental Management Act, Cap. 191 R.E. 2022.

Local Government (District Authorities) Act, Cap. 287 R.E. 2002.

Village Land Act, Cap. 114 R.E. 2019.

Wildlife Conservation Act, Cap. 283 R.E. 2022.

Statutes and Legal Instruments (Other Jurisdictions)

Constitution of Kenya (2010).

Environment and Land Court Act (Kenya), No. 19 of 2011.

National Environmental Management Act (South Africa), No. 107 of 1998.

Wildlife Conservation and Management Act (Kenya), No. 47 of 2013.

International and Regional Instruments

African Union. (2003). *Revised African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (Maputo Convention)*.

Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), adopted 5 June 1992, entered into force 29 December 1993.

Policy Reports, Guidelines, and Manuals

Department of Environmental Affairs (South Africa). (2016). *Guidelines on Mediation and Conciliation in Environmental Disputes*.

FAO. (2023). *Managing Conflicts Between People and Wildlife: Climate Change Dimensions*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization.

Kenya Revenue Authority. (2021). *ADR Framework Manual*. Retrieved from: <https://www.kra.go.ke> on 26 July 2025.

Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism (Tanzania). (2017). *Wildlife Sector Review and Governance Report*.

Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism (Tanzania). (2021). *Wildlife Sector Status Report*.

TAWIRI. (2019). *Policy Brief on Human-Wildlife Conflicts in Tanzania*.

Tanzania Natural Resource Forum (TNRF). (2016). *Community Experiences of Wildlife Compensation and Conflict Resolution in Tanzania*.

UNEP. (2009). *Training Manual on Environmental Mediation*. Nairobi: United Nations Environment Programme.

WWF Tanzania. (2020). *Human-Wildlife Conflict Mitigation Strategy 2020–2025*.